

Supplementary Information

Ultra-fast Spectroscopy for High-Throughput and Interactive Quantum Chemistry

Francesco Bosia¹, Thomas Weymuth², and Markus Reiher³

Laboratory of Physical Chemistry, ETH Zurich, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

April 14, 2022

Contents

1	Trajectories	2
2	Parameters and Connectivity for MD trajectory	2
3	IR Spectroscopy	8
3.1	Reference Calculation	8
3.2	Partial Hessian Approach	9
4	UV/Vis Spectroscopy	13
4.1	Reference Calculation	13
4.2	Two-electron Integrals in Singlet and Triplet CSF	13
4.3	Improved Initial Guess	15

¹ORCID: 0000-0001-6021-7672

²ORCID: 0000-0001-7102-7022

³Corresponding author; e-mail: markus.reiher@phys.chem.ethz.ch, ORCID: 0000-0002-9508-1565

1 Trajectories

Figure 1: DFTB3 electronic energy (blue) and sum of the atomic gradient norms (olive) of each structure along the trajectory **T1**. Points are added at the structure index at which a new IR spectrum calculation is started.

In Figures 1 and 2 we show the energies and the gradients along the trajectories **T1** and **T2**, respectively. The trajectories are available in the concatenated XYZ format in the compressed folder "trajectories.zip". The IR spectrum calculation is started as soon as the gradient is lower than the gradient threshold $\epsilon_{\text{grad}} = 0.55$ hartree bohr⁻¹. The structure indices in the trajectories at which an IR spectrum calculation is started is indicated with a dot in the plots. The indices are 177 and 184 for **T1** and **T2**, respectively.

2 Parameters and Connectivity for MD trajectory

The **MD** trajectory was generated by a force-field molecular dynamics simulation of allylphenylether in vacuo with the leap-frog algorithm and an integration step of 1 fs, of which 1 structure was sampled every 250 steps. The force-field parameters were optimized in a system-focused fashion according to the SFAM method¹ with RI/PBE-D3BJ/def2-SVP and the def2/J auxiliary basis.

Figure 2: DFTB3 electronic energy (blue) and sum of the atomic gradient norms (olive) of each structure along the trajectory **T2**. Points are added at the structure index at which a new IR spectrum calculation is started.

In the "Connectivity.dat" file each line represents an atom index in the molecule, with the same order given by the xyz file containing the structure coordinates. The indices in the line are the indices the atoms forming a covalent bond to it.

Connectivity.dat:

```

1  5  11
0  2  6
1  3  7
2  4  8
3  5  9
0  4  10
1
2
3
4
5
0  12
11 13 16 19
12 15 17
17
13

```

12
13 14 18
17
12

The total potential energy E_{MM} in the SFAM force field is given as the sum of energy contributions defining the force-field,

$$E_{\text{MM}} = E_r + E_\alpha + E_\theta + E_\phi + E_{\text{estat}} + E_{\text{disp}} + E_{\text{rep}} + E_{\text{hb}} . \quad (1)$$

We will briefly summarize the calculation of the energy terms to indicate the role of the parameters in "Parameters.dat". For a more thorough discussion, we refer to the discussion contained in the original publication.¹ The covalent terms are calculated from displacement of interatomic distances r , bonds angles α , dihedral angles θ , and improper dihedral angles ϕ from equilibrium values. The potential energy contribution from bonds,

$$E_r = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{A,B} k_r^{AB} (r^{AB} - r_0^{AB})^2 , \quad (2)$$

and from the bond angles,

$$E_\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{A,B,C} k_\alpha^{ABC} (\alpha^{ABC} - \alpha_0^{ABC})^2 , \quad (3)$$

is described with harmonic potentials around the equilibrium distance between the atom pair (A, B) , r_0^{AB} , or the equilibrium angle formed by the atom triple (A, B, C) , α_0^{ABC} . In the "! bonds" ("! angles") section, the first two (three) columns indicate the atoms defining the interaction, and the last two columns define r_0^{AB} (α_0^{ABC}) and the force constant k_r^{AB} (k_α^{ABC}). For the definition of the dihedral angle potential energy term,

$$E_\theta = \sum_{A,B,C,D} V_\theta^{ABCD} (1 - \cos(n^{ABCD}\theta^{ABCD} - \theta_0^{ABCD})) , \quad (4)$$

three parameters are needed: the half energy barrier height of the dihedral angle, V_θ^{ABCD} , the number of minima of the potential energy term, n_θ^{ABCD} , and the phase shift, θ_0^{ABCD} . In the "! dihedral" block, the first four columns indicate the atom types defining the dihedral angle, followed by V_θ , θ_0 and n_θ . The potential energy term stemming from improper dihedrals is given by

$$E_\varphi = \sum_{X,A,B,C} \begin{cases} k_\varphi^{XABC} (\varphi^{XABC} - \varphi_0^{XABC})^2 & \text{if } \varphi_0^{XABC} \leq \tilde{\varphi} \\ k_\varphi^{XABC} (\cos \varphi^{XABC} - \cos \varphi_0^{XABC})^2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} , \quad (5)$$

and, as before, the "! impropers" block define the improper dihedral through the atom types in the first four columns, followed by φ_0 , which is 0 for a planar fragment,

and the force constant k_φ . The partial charges enter the definition of the electrostatic potential energy term for non-bonded atoms,

$$E_{\text{estat}} = \sum_{A<B} f_{\text{estat}}^{AB} \frac{q_A q_B}{r^{AB}}, \quad (6)$$

where f_{estat}^{AB} is a scaling factor equal to zero if A and B are bonded, and equal to one otherwise. r^{AB} is the distance between A and B . The dispersion term is defined as

$$E_{\text{disp}} = - \sum_{A<B} f_{\text{disp}}^{AB} \left(\frac{C_6^{AB}}{(r^{AB})^6 + (f_{\text{damp}}^{AB})^6} + s_8 \frac{C_8^{AB}}{(r^{AB})^8 + (f_{\text{damp}}^{AB})^8} \right), \quad (7)$$

with the Becke–Johnson damping function

$$f_{\text{damp}}^{AB} = a_1 R_0^{AB} + a_2. \quad (8)$$

The value of R_0 , as well as the calculation of the C_6 and C_8 coefficients is taken from Grimme’s D3 model.² The f_{disp}^{AB} is zero if the atoms A and B are bonded, and one otherwise, and the other parameters are listed under the ”! vdw” block. We refer to the original SFAM publication¹ for the further potential energy terms, and will not discuss them here further, as they are not influenced by the parameters given in the file ”Parameters.dat”.

Parameters.dat:

MM parameters generated by SCINE

! bonds

C3_C201	C3_H1C2	1.41099	695.396
C3_C201	O2_C2	1.36673	630.083
C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	1.403	770.725
C3_H1C2	C3_H2C1	1.34303	1122.94
C3_H1C2	C4_H2C101	1.50551	466.377
C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	1.10055	712.651
C3_H2C1	H_C3_H2C1	1.10217	680.773
C4_H2C101	H_C4_H2C101	1.11323	647.262
C4_H2C101	O2_C2	1.42465	432.615

! angles

C3_C201	C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	119.812	167.559
C3_C201	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	119.592	83.3537
C3_C201	O2_C2	C4_H2C101	119.431	141.092
C3_H1C2	C3_C201	C3_H1C2	119.619	148.424
C3_H1C2	C3_C201	O2_C2	120.189	165.85
C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	120.252	150.093
C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	120.053	82.5842

C3_H1C2	C3_H2C1	H_C3_H2C1	121.546	72.4404
C3_H1C2	C4_H2C101	H_C4_H2C101	110.192	97.32
C3_H1C2	C4_H2C101	O2_C2	113.571	168.655
C3_H2C1	C3_H1C2	C4_H2C101	124.742	86.1105
C3_H2C1	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	120.364	73.6832
C4_H2C101	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	114.85	82.1241
H_C3_H2C1	C3_H2C1	H_C3_H2C1	116.906	48.9516
H_C4_H2C101	C4_H2C101	H_C4_H2C101	107.309	68.1611
H_C4_H2C101	C4_H2C101	O2_C2	107.561	116.02

! dihedrals

X	C4_H2C101	O2_C2	X	0.28849	180	3
X	C3_H2C1	C3_H1C2	X	10	0	2
X	C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	X	10	0	2
X	C3_C201	C3_H1C2	X	10	0	2

! impropers

C3_C201	C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	O2_C2	0	50
C3_H1C2	C3_C201	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	0	50
C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H1C2	0	50
C3_H1C2	C3_H2C1	C4_H2C101	H_C3_H1C2	0	50
C3_H2C1	C3_H1C2	H_C3_H2C1	H_C3_H2C1	0	50

! charges

C0	0.0839732
C1	-0.11379
C2	-0.102956
C3	-0.118641
C4	-0.103963
C5	-0.12655
H6	0.107752
H7	0.102386
H8	0.0994872
H9	0.101389
H10	0.0981492
O11	-0.207987
C12	-0.0512428
C13	-0.104271
H14	0.101327
H15	0.107461
H16	0.117194
C17	-0.190356
H18	0.0963562

H19 0.104279

! vdw

a1 0.1

s8 4.6

a2 7.1

! c6 coefficients

25.161

25.1927 25.3115

25.2037 25.3226 25.3546

25.1881 25.307 25.3389 25.35

25.1813 25.3001 25.332 25.3431 25.3274

8.78245 8.8242 8.83543 8.83934 8.83382 8.8314

8.78265 8.82439 8.83563 8.83953 8.83401 8.83159 3.08954

8.78242 8.82417 8.8354 8.8393 8.83378 8.83136 3.08946 3.08953

8.7826 8.82435 8.83558 8.83949 8.83397 8.83155 3.08953 3.08959

3.08951

8.78157 8.82332 8.83455 8.83845 8.83293 8.83051 3.08916 3.08923

3.08915 3.08921

15.6243 15.6883 15.7055 15.7115 15.703 15.6993 5.4285 5.42861

5.42848 5.42858 5.42801

21.2887 21.3834 21.4089 21.4178 21.4053 21.3998 7.45375 7.45391

7.45372 7.45387 7.45303 13.593

25.3246 25.4443 25.4765 25.4877 25.4718 25.4649 8.88216 8.88236

8.88213 8.88231 8.88127 15.7774 21.5152

8.78425 8.826 8.83724 8.84114 8.83563 8.8332 3.09011 3.09018

3.0901 3.09016 3.0898 5.4295 7.45521 8.88398

8.78261 8.82435 8.83559 8.83949 8.83397 8.83155 3.08953 3.08959

3.08951 3.08958 3.08921 5.42858 7.45387 8.88232 3.09016

8.78569 8.82745 8.83869 8.84259 8.83707 8.83465 3.09062 3.09069

3.09061 3.09067 3.09031 5.4303 7.45638 8.88544 3.09125 3.09067

25.32 25.4396 25.4718 25.483 25.4672 25.4602 8.88052 8.88072

8.88049 8.88067 8.87963 15.7748 21.5115 25.6056 8.88234 8.88068

8.8838

8.78409 8.82585 8.83708 8.84099 8.83547 8.83305 3.09005 3.09012

3.09004 3.09011 3.08974 5.42941 7.45508 8.88382 3.09069 3.09011

3.0912 8.88218

8.78523 8.82699 8.83823 8.84214 8.83662 8.8342 3.09046 3.09052

3.09044 3.09051 3.09014 5.43004 7.45601 8.88498 3.09109 3.09051

3.0916 8.88334 3.09104

3 IR Spectroscopy

3.1 Reference Calculation

The calculation providing a reference for the semiempirical methods PM6 and DFTB3 was carried out with the Orca 4.2.0 software with the input file

```
! PBE0 def2-TZVP def2/J Opt Freq RIJCOSX Grid3 FinalGrid5 GridX4 D3 PAL6
%maxcore 2000
%scf
Convergence VeryTight
end

* xyzfile 0 1 T2.xyz
```

and the coordinate file T2.xyz

55

C	10.7732444487	-1.0484845729	-0.4578940010
C	9.3652488854	-0.4765249305	-0.3080317298
C	9.1979915741	0.8294891583	-1.0971583768
C	7.8182503372	1.4701849896	-0.8957576339
C	7.6064363009	2.0322669086	0.5176849979
C	8.5152856345	3.1761868114	0.8508685825
C	8.6311862286	3.7319995342	2.0616358761
C	7.8728272052	3.2916545306	3.2797422717
C	7.5941055813	4.4344885718	4.2102785770
H	8.6127965666	3.1797643823	6.8279873718
O	6.6211208612	5.2384221043	3.6390629929
C	8.1108820929	4.7037695078	5.4188778808
C	9.1324691353	3.8542427877	6.1100851701
C	10.1298127903	4.7008294358	6.8502900314
C	11.3158073740	5.0885556450	6.3707336163
C	11.8267263062	4.7518587968	5.0005096499
C	13.2566205996	5.1679766754	4.8179304013
C	13.6652845118	6.2550467294	4.1563684804
C	12.7602932047	7.2503121143	3.4904430527
C	12.3700902124	8.3564900613	4.4817154826
C	11.4614862698	9.3995895206	3.8211183251
C	11.1503250506	10.5124273939	4.7742701762
O	9.8175910346	10.8572027286	4.6637089120
O	11.8529039121	11.1096615405	5.5534800278
H	10.8831590451	-1.9835454074	0.1021775486

H	11.5323359986	-0.3515556454	-0.0841921690
H	11.0134716254	-1.2625393685	-1.5053184167
H	9.1484110295	-0.2958901293	0.7637305457
H	8.6183779784	-1.2199743268	-0.6470312490
H	9.3564521106	0.6340972492	-2.1754541707
H	9.9901808292	1.5454360579	-0.8028868301
H	7.0258794966	0.7265889597	-1.1115368272
H	7.6784328219	2.2776386805	-1.6413876486
H	7.7372151898	1.2162923772	1.2599149449
H	6.5509247662	2.3668743799	0.6220765823
H	9.1054893568	3.5576278594	0.0148823536
H	9.3087656156	4.5703038841	2.2287800435
H	8.4481020259	2.4970872200	3.8055538293
H	6.9006859186	2.8265452900	2.9948579382
H	6.4107389887	6.0256537940	4.1948854454
H	7.7936932547	5.5798468561	5.9806804521
H	9.6468729898	3.1793342067	5.3928240249
H	9.8096046537	5.0025329832	7.8484248416
H	11.9858302853	5.7022141807	6.9761597369
H	11.1674889548	5.2340990083	4.2416525703
H	11.7304938091	3.6596790755	4.8115244598
H	13.9800479346	4.4985839338	5.2878326768
H	14.7281608427	6.4887069919	4.0756368862
H	11.8470719418	6.7499479620	3.1033169140
H	13.2626169008	7.6855102176	2.6036456287
H	13.2800273418	8.8484826262	4.8844164796
H	11.8587146595	7.9050185476	5.3573297433
H	10.5222001053	8.9295578515	3.4529512481
H	11.9509000273	9.8311808471	2.9196172042
H	9.5603714949	11.6027113118	5.2672785866

The absolute value of the elements of the reference Hessian matrix and its deviation from the ones calculated with the PM6 and DFTB3 methods is depicted in Figure 3. It is obvious that the DFTB3 method is better at reproducing the Hessian matrix elements and the frequencies (see main text) obtained with the reference DFT calculation.

3.2 Partial Hessian Approach

Here, we list the fragments of the structure **T1.II.VT** that needed to be reevaluated for each threshold ϵ_{RMSD} .

Figure 3: Absolute elements and deviations of the Hessian matrix of the structure corresponding to the first minimum along the trajectory **T2** calculated with DFT (PBE0/def2-TZVP/D3), DFTB3 and PM6. Top panel: absolute value of the elements of the Hessian matrix calculated with the DFT method. Bottom-left panel: absolute deviation of the elements of the Hessian matrix calculated with DFT and the one calculated with PM6. Bottom-right panel: absolute deviation of the elements of the Hessian matrix calculated with DFT and the one calculated with DFTB3. Each pixel in a panel corresponds to an element of the Hessian matrix, darker colors correspond to stronger deviations. The calculated matrices are sparse, therefore most of the matrix elements have a negligible absolute deviation.

Figure 4: Result of the alignment of the **T1.II.VT** structure with the **T1.I.VT** structure for various values of ϵ_{RMSD} . Atoms whose coordinates differ from the ones in the structure corresponding to the optimized **T1.I** structure after the iterative alignment are coloured in red. The Hessian matrix elements corresponding to the grey fragments of the molecule are not evaluated, but subsumed by the ones calculated in the previous minimum.

Figure 5: Result of the iterative alignment of the **T2.II.VT** structure (green) with the **T2.I.VT** structure (cyan). No common structural fragments are found by the iterative alignment algorithm.

For the trajectory **T2** no common fragments were found, as the keto–enol tautomerism in the middle of the molecule results in an enol where the aliphatic chains are in cis conformation to one another. This global rearrangement of the molecule does not abide to the assumption of the partial Hessian approach in that the structure distortion from **T2.I.VT** to **T2.II.VT** is not local. The iterative alignment of **T2.II.VT** to **T2.I.VT** does not result in the identification of atoms whose coordinates were not affected from the reaction. As a consequence, the whole Hessian matrix needs to be evaluated.

4 UV/Vis Spectroscopy

4.1 Reference Calculation

The UV/Vis reference calculations were carried out with the spin-component scaled second-order approximate coupled cluster singles and doubles model (SCS-CC2).^{3,4} In Table 1, we provide the vertical transition energies obtained with SCS-CC2/cc-pVDZ with those obtained with the more accurate, but prohibitively costly CC3 model⁵ with the same basis set. The vertical excitation energies calculated with the two methods were similar. Therefore, we did not expect significant contributions from double excitations to the description of the excited states, and the SCS-CC2 method was deemed reliable for the system under study. CC3 calculations were carried out with the e^T 1.0.7 program,⁶ SCS-CC2 calculations with the Turbomole 7.4.1 software package.⁷

Table 1: Vertical excitation energies in eV calculated with the SCS-CC2 and the CC3 models with the cc-pVDZ basis set of the first structure along the trajectory MD described in the main text. The excited states were matched by identifying the dominant amplitudes characterizing the excitations.

Transition label	Dominant excitation	SCS-CC2 [eV]	CC3 [eV]
$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	HOMO-LUMO	4.898	4.877
$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	HOMO-(LUMO+1)	6.200	6.258

Furthermore, vertical transition energies calculated with the TD-DFTB method were compared with those calculated with PBE/def2-TZVP/TD-DFT, PBE0/def2-TZVP/TD-DFT, and the SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP. The results of this comparison are summarized in Table 2. The TD-DFTB calculations were carried out with the SPARROW program,⁸ and the TD-DFT calculations with the Orca 4.2.0 software package.^{9,10}

4.2 Two-electron Integrals in Singlet and Triplet CSF

In the following we outline the contraction of the two-electron integrals in the CSF basis for the singlet and triplet electronic transitions. We define the expectation value of the operator \hat{O} over two arbitrary singly excited determinants as

$$\hat{O} = \sum_{pq\sigma} \sum_{rst} \left| \Phi_{pq\sigma} \right\rangle \left(p_{\sigma} q_{\sigma} \left| r_{\tau} s_{\tau} \right. \right) - \left(p_{\sigma} r_{\tau} \left| q_{\sigma} s_{\tau} \right. \right) \left\langle \Phi_{rst} \right|, \quad (9)$$

Table 2: Vertical transition energies in eV calculated with TD-DFTB, PBE/def2-TZVP/TD-DFT, PBE0/def2-TZVP/TD-DFT, and SCS-CC2/def2-TZVP. The excited states calculated with different methods were matched by identifying the dominant single orbital substitutions characterizing the excitation. The excitation labels are those resulting from the SCS-CC2 calculation.

Excitation label	Dominant excitation	TD-DFTB PBE/[eV]	TD-DFT PBE0/[eV]	TD-DFT SCS-CC2/[eV]	SCS-CC2/[eV]
$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$	HOMO–LUMO	4.257	4.034	4.928	4.797
$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$	HOMO–(LUMO+1)	4.698	4.707	5.341	6.650
$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$	(HUMO-1)–LUMO	5.266	4.978	6.235	7.009
$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	HOMO–(LUMO+2)	5.344	5.448	5.790	6.002
$S_0 \rightarrow S_7$	(HUMO-2)–LUMO	5.873	5.541	6.629	7.738

and evaluate the expectation value of this operator over the singlet and triplet CSF constructed from the same determinants combined according to

$$\begin{aligned}
{}^1\Psi_{ia} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Phi_{ia\alpha} + \Phi_{ia\beta}) \\
{}^3\Psi_{ia} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Phi_{ia\alpha} - \Phi_{ia\beta}), \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle {}^1\Psi_{pq} | \mathcal{O} | {}^1\Psi_{rs} \rangle &= \\
& \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | + \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \right) \left(\sum_{p'q'\sigma} \sum_{r's'\tau} |\Phi_{p'q'\sigma}\rangle (p'_\sigma q'_\sigma | r'_\tau s'_\tau) \right. \\
& \left. - (p'_\sigma r'_\tau | q'_\sigma s'_\tau) \langle \Phi_{r's'\tau} | \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(|\Phi_{rs\alpha}\rangle + |\Phi_{rs\beta}\rangle \right) \\
& = \\
& \frac{1}{2} \left(\langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | \Phi_{pq\alpha} \rangle (p_\alpha q_\alpha | r_\alpha s_\alpha) - (p_\alpha r_\alpha | q_\alpha s_\alpha) \langle \Phi_{rs\alpha} | \Phi_{rs\alpha} \rangle \right. \\
& + \langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | \Phi_{pq\alpha} \rangle (p_\alpha q_\alpha | r_\beta s_\beta) - (p_\alpha r_\beta | q_\alpha s_\beta) \langle \Phi_{rs\beta} | \Phi_{rs\beta} \rangle \\
& + \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \Phi_{pq\beta} \rangle (p_\beta q_\beta | r_\beta s_\beta) - (p_\beta r_\alpha | q_\beta s_\alpha) \langle \Phi_{rs\alpha} | \Phi_{rs\alpha} \rangle \\
& \left. + \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \Phi_{pq\beta} \rangle (p_\beta q_\beta | r_\beta s_\beta) - (p_\beta r_\beta | q_\beta s_\beta) \langle \Phi_{rs\beta} | \Phi_{rs\beta} \rangle \right), \tag{11}
\end{aligned}$$

and, noting that the spatial parts of the molecular orbitals are equal for opposite spin partners in restricted calculations, i.e. $p_\alpha = p|\alpha\rangle$, and that integrals over orbitals of

opposite spin vanish,

$$\langle {}^1\Psi_{pq} | \mathcal{O} | {}^1\Psi_{rs} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \left(4 \left(pq | rs \right) - 2 \left(pr | qs \right) \right) = 2 \left(pq | rs \right) - \left(pr | qs \right). \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the integral over triplet CSF

$$\begin{aligned} \langle {}^3\Psi_{pq} | \mathcal{O} | {}^3\Psi_{rs} \rangle &= \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | - \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \right) \left(\sum_{p'q'\sigma} \sum_{r's'\tau} | \Phi_{p'q'\sigma} \rangle \left(p'_\sigma q'_\sigma | r'_\tau s'_\tau \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \left(p'_\sigma r'_\tau | q'_\sigma s'_\tau \right) \langle \Phi_{r's'\tau} | \right) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(| \Phi_{rs\alpha} \rangle - | \Phi_{rs\beta} \rangle \right) \\ &= \\ & \frac{1}{2} \left(\langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | \Phi_{pq\alpha} \rangle \left(p_\alpha q_\alpha | r_\alpha s_\alpha \right) - \left(p_\alpha r_\alpha | q_\alpha s_\alpha \right) \langle \Phi_{rs\alpha} | \Phi_{rs\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ & \quad - \langle \Phi_{pq\alpha} | \Phi_{pq\alpha} \rangle \left(p_\alpha q_\alpha | r_\beta s_\beta \right) - \left(p_\alpha r_\beta | q_\alpha s_\beta \right) \langle \Phi_{rs\beta} | \Phi_{rs\beta} \rangle \\ & \quad - \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \Phi_{pq\beta} \rangle \left(p_\beta q_\beta | r_\beta s_\beta \right) - \left(p_\beta r_\alpha | q_\beta s_\alpha \right) \langle \Phi_{rs\alpha} | \Phi_{rs\alpha} \rangle \\ & \quad \left. + \langle \Phi_{pq\beta} | \Phi_{pq\beta} \rangle \left(p_\beta q_\beta | r_\beta s_\beta \right) - \left(p_\beta r_\beta | q_\beta s_\beta \right) \langle \Phi_{rs\beta} | \Phi_{rs\beta} \rangle \right), \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

can be simplified to

$$\langle {}^3\Psi_{pq} | \mathcal{O} | {}^3\Psi_{rs} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \left(-2 \left(pr | qs \right) \right) = - \left(pr | qs \right). \quad (14)$$

4.3 Improved Initial Guess

In an iterative subspace diagonalization algorithm, the quality of the initial guess is a key ingredient for computational and numerical performance. If the matrix being diagonalized is diagonally-dominant, a diagonal guess is a good approximation for the solution of the eigenvalue problem. A better initial guess may be provided by the assumption that similar structures will have similar electronic excited states. The excited states calculated for a structure can be employed as initial guess for similar structures. As a generalization of this choice, a direct inversion of the iterative subspace (DIIS) methodology was developed along the lines of the DIIS method we developed¹¹ for the self-consistent field calculation convergence acceleration in interactive explorations. In our newly developed DIIS method, we predict new guess vectors for the $(s + 1)$ -th molecular structure with coordinates $\mathbf{R}^{(s+1)}$ as a linear combination of K previous excited-state solution vectors weighted by coefficients,

c_k , given by the least-squares minimization of the error \mathbf{E} in

$$\mathbf{R}^{(s+1)} = \mathbf{E} + \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} c_k \mathbf{R}^{(s-k)}, \quad (15)$$

leading to a DIIS-like problem whose solution provides the weights c_k with which the excited states of the previous K structures enter the new guess. We explored whether the DIIS extrapolation technique of Eq. (15) improved the time needed to calculate the first 30 excited states of the structures in trajectories **MD** and **T1**.

Both the type of initial guess (standard guess, previous solution and linear combination of previous solutions) and the number of the initial guess vectors were analyzed. We calculated the mean timing for the calculation of a spectrum along the **MD** and **T1** trajectory with the different initial guess types and either one or four initial guess vectors per desired root, i.e. an initial guess composed by 30 or 120 vectors. If more than one initial guess vector per root was desired, the previous solution or linear combination of previous solutions occupied the first 30 initial vectors. Standard initial guess vectors were added until the required amount of initial guess vectors was reached. The results are provided in Table 3. Fig. 6 presents the timings for each structure in the respective trajectory and each initial guess.

In Fig. 6, we show the results of the comparison of timings for this calculation with (i) a standard diagonal initial guess with four trial vectors per root as described in the theory section (cf. main text), (ii) an initial guess composed of the solution of the previous structure with standard guess vectors up to four vectors per root, and (iii) an initial guess formed by the DIIS approach with standard guess vectors up to four vectors per root. Adding more than one guess vector per root was found to be beneficial for all calculations. In Table 3, we showed that employing an improved guess has a positive impact for reducing the computational time needed to calculate the UV/Vis spectra along the trajectory **T1** with an initial guess composed of one guess vector per desired root. Nevertheless, no consistent improvement in the computational efficiency was achieved for all cases under study. A linear combination of previous solutions provided by the DIIS algorithm also showed no difference to taking the initial guess to be the solution of the excited-state problem in only the previous structure along the trajectory.

Figure 6: Time needed to calculate the first 30 excited states of the structures along the trajectory **MD** (left panels) and **T1** (right panels) with the TD-DFTB method and the standard diagonal initial guess (blue), described in the main text, with the solution of the previous structure as an initial guess (orange), and with the DIIS procedure applied to the last ten solutions (green). A UV/Vis spectrum is calculated for each structure along the trajectory. Top row: the initial guess is composed of one initial vector per desired root, corresponding to an initial subspace size of 30. Bottom row: the initial guess is composed of four initial vectors per desired root, corresponding to an initial subspace size of 120. The "Previous Solution" and "DIIS" guesses, composed by one vector per desired root, were complemented with standard guess vectors until the initial subspace size of 120 was reached.

Table 3: Mean times to calculate an UV/Vis spectrum along the trajectories **MD** and **T1**. Within each trajectory, the calculations differ in the initial subspace construction method, and the initial subspace size.

Trajectory	Initial Guess	Initial subspace size	Time [ms]
MD	Standard	30	39.7
	Previous Solution	30	49.6
	DIIS	30	50.4
	Standard	120	25.0
	Previous Solution	120	35.7
	DIIS	120	37.1
T1	Standard	30	290
	Previous Solution	30	224
	DIIS	30	230
	Standard	120	152
	Previous Solution	120	166
	DIIS	120	168

i

References

- [1] Brunken, C.; Reiher, M. Self-Parametrizing System-Focused Atomistic Models. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2020**, *16*, 1646–1665.
- [2] Grimme, S.; Antony, J.; Ehrlich, S.; Krieg, H. A consistent and accurate *ab initio* parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *132*, 154104.
- [3] Christiansen, O.; Koch, H.; Jørgensen, P. The second-order approximate coupled cluster singles and doubles model CC2. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1995**, *243*, 409–418.
- [4] Hellweg, A.; Grün, S. A.; Hättig, C. Benchmarking the performance of spin-component scaled CC2 in ground and electronically excited states. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *10*, 4119–4127.
- [5] Koch, H.; Christiansen, O.; Jørgensen, P.; Sanchez de Merás, A. M.; Helgaker, T. The CC3 model: An iterative coupled cluster approach including connected triples. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1997**, *106*, 1808–1818.

- [6] Folkestad, S. D. et al. e^T 1.0: An open source electronic structure program with emphasis on coupled cluster and multilevel methods. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *152*, 184103.
- [7] Ahlrichs, R.; Bär, M.; Häser, M.; Horn, H.; Kölmel, C. Electronic structure calculations on workstation computers: The program system Turbomole. *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1989**, *162*, 165–169.
- [8] Bosia, F.; Husch, T.; Müller, C. H.; Polonius, S.; Sobez, J.-G.; Steiner, M.; Unsleber, J. P.; Vaucher, A. C.; Weymuth, T.; Reiher, M. qcscine/sparrow: Release 3.0.0. 2021; Zenodo.
- [9] Neese, F. The ORCA program system. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2012**, *2*, 73–78.
- [10] Neese, F. Software update: the ORCA program system, version 4.0. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Comput. Mol. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, e1327.
- [11] Mühlbach, A. H.; Vaucher, A. C.; Reiher, M. Accelerating Wave Function Convergence in Interactive Quantum Chemical Reactivity Studies. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **2016**, *12*, 1228–1235.